

Literature review on multiple values concepts in academic literature

Results report

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Objectives

This literature review was meant to provide an overview of temporal and thematic trends regarding the use of diverse value concepts in the academic literature.

Methods

The Stage III review is a quantitative and qualitative scoping review (Pham et al., 2014). It used an adapted Stage I protocol¹ with the following search terms employed in Scopus for the period 2005-2019 to identify potentially relevant literature: TITLE-ABS-KEY(((valu* OR wellbeing OR well-being OR "quality of life") AND (nature OR ecosystem OR biodiversity OR landscape) OR "environmental valu*" OR "human-nature relat*" OR "society nature relat*")) AND PUBYEAR > 2004 AND SUBJAREA (ARTS OR BUSI OR DECI OR ECON OR PSYC OR SOCI OR ENVI OR EARTH OR MULT OR AGRI OR Undefined). This procedure produced a corpus of 148,082 abstracts².

Using an artificial intelligence (AI) procedure in the R library STM (Roberts, 2013), the entirety of the initial dataset was processed for a preliminary topic model. Data processing included word stemming, punctuation removal, stop word removal, etc. Initially, 40 topics were modelled. The algorithm assigns each abstract in the database to one of these topics, based on its predominant topic by weight (i.e. an abstract which contained 55% of topic 4 and 45% of topic 18, would be labeled as a topic 4 abstract). Then, eight exemplar abstracts were extracted from each topic to manually interpret the meaning of each topic – semantically inferring what category each topic referred to by reading the top abstract in each topic and the most diagnostic words in each topic. Three coders (including two subject matter experts and a TSU assessment coordinator) analysed each exemplar abstract for each topic to screen and determine eligibility, based on relevance to the aims of the *Values Assessment*, on a three-point scale (not all relevant, somewhat relevant, very relevant). If two of the three coders found a topic to be either somewhat or very relevant, it was included in the assessment.

Topics that were categorized by at least 2 coders as irrelevant were removed, such as:

¹ Systematic review on the conceptualizations of values (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4071755>)

² Literature review on multiple values concepts in academic literature (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4396319>)

“The aim of the study was to compare the extraction efficiency of headspace and solvent extraction methods on watermelon juice flavour. Solid-phase microextraction (SPME) and solvent-assisted flavour evaporation (SAFE) techniques were employed to extract the volatiles from watermelon juice. Aroma compounds were separated and analysed through gas chromatography-olfactometry-mass spectrometry (GC-MS/O) equipped with DB-5 and DB-Wax capillary columns. Forty-seven compounds were identified by SPME (30) and SAFE (28). These compounds included 7 aldehydes, 10 olefinic aldehydes, 14 alcohols, 7 sulfur compounds, 5 ketones, and 4 miscellaneous compounds. SPME extracted the saturated aldehydes, olefinic aldehydes, alcohols, and ketones effectively, whereas SAFE exerted better efficiency to extract sulfur compounds.”

These identification, screening, eligibility and inclusion steps resulted in a final analytic dataset of $n=40,133$ to which we applied another AI topic modelling algorithm, testing two models: 40 and 60 topics. The 60-topic model produced more detailed topics and was chosen for better conduct qualitative analysis of thematic trends. To interpret thematic content, the coding exercise was repeated, selecting eight exemplars per topic and coding them for relevance. At the same time, we classified the topics as per their relationship to IPBES’s broad disciplinary categories to valuing nature: Biophysical, Economic, Health, Socio-cultural and ILK. As in the first stage of analysis, if two coders categorized a topic as somewhat or very relevant, it was kept within the final analytic dataset. Applied to the 60 topics modelled, this process produced a final dataset with 46 topics.

With these data, we graphed temporal trends for the entire dataset and disciplinary category. Plus, descriptive statistics were used to determine the percentage of studies (categorized per disciplinary research orientation) that were published in journals based on their self-identified research domain. As per the Scopus typology, research domains were: Life, Physical, Health and Social Sciences. It was possible for a journal to self-identify with more than one category, and some journals did not classify themselves at all (NA).

Finally, we identified interrelationships between AI-identified topics and IPBES categories, using the core set of 46 topics (Table 1). We first created a correlation network, a graphical depiction of a correlation matrix between pairs of topics, using the R package *qgraph* (Epskamp et al. 2012). The layout of the network structure is organized using the Fruchterman–Reingold algorithm (Fruchterman & Reingold, 1991), a force-directed layout (Figure 2). In this layout, nodes (or topics, in the present case) that are more interrelated are placed closer together. Topics that have weaker connections, and less central to the semantic content of the articles, are located on the periphery of the graph. How often topics co-occur in an article is indicated by the thickness of the edges (links between nodes), while the valence of relationships is depicted in blue for positive relationships and orange for negative relationships. The thickness and colour of the edges are based on partial correlations. So, topics that are most likely to co-occur in the same article will be joined with a thick, blue edge while topics that are not likely to occur together will be joined with an orange link. We also scaled the size of the nodes to reflect topic proportions within the model (multiplied by a constant factor for readability). The colour of each node was determined by the membership of the topic within one of our categories (i.e., biophysical, economic, ILK, health, or other).

Results

Temporal trends: Since 2005, this body of literature has increased from 924 publications in 2005 to 6,213 in 2019 (Figure 1.A). While increases occurred for the Biophysical, Economic, Socio-Cultural and ILK domains, Health did not appear as an AI-identified category. A plurality of studies (44%) have a Biophysical orientation, and this literature is most likely (75%) to be published in journals from Life and Physical Sciences. Yet, a substantial proportion is found in interdisciplinary journals (Figure 1.B). The greatest increases in research productivity were registered in the realms of Economics and ILK. Nonetheless, studies with a socio-cultural focus were the second most numerous within this literature (28%), tending to be published in Social Science journals (58%) and to a lesser degree in other interdisciplinary outlets (9%).

Disciplinary orientation: Overall, of the total identified research topics (n=46), 65% were classified as pertaining to a Biophysical disciplinary orientation (n=30). From the remaining studies, 14% (n=6) were Socio-cultural, 7% were Economic (n=3), and 2.2% were ILK (n=1). No thematic grouping was identified as primarily Health-related. Another 13% could not be classified into just one disciplinary domain and were labelled Other (n=6).

Figure 1. Chapter 2’s Stage III literature review identified 40,133 abstracts in Scopus about nature’s diverse values. Data are presented as each analytic category’s relative frequency as a percentage of the entire database (%). (A) An artificial intelligence (AI) algorithm produced 60 categories that were manually classified by the predominant research topics for each, resulting in 46 categories (30 biophysical, 3 economic, 6 socio-cultural, 1 ILK, and 6 “other”). (B) Journal disciplinary domain was based on self-identified categories in Scopus: Life, Physical, Health, Social Sciences or an interdisciplinary combination. NA are journals that did report a discipline.

Research topics: The topical structure of how articles related to one another revealed some interesting trends (Figure 2). First, although the majority of the topics fell within the biophysical category, these were not the most central topics in our analysis. Rather, topics from the socio-cultural category and even the topic from the ILK category emerged as more central than any given topic from the biophysical category. This result could in part be an artifact of the selection criteria (i.e. we specifically looked for articles that were about human values toward nature), but it is telling that the most central topics in our overall analysis contained words such as cultural, value, identity, manage, risk, decision, climate, develop, and sustain. This analysis also suggests that biophysical topics mostly emerge in relation to other biophysical topics (i.e. this field appears more insular than other categorizations such as socio-cultural or economic).

Network Graph by IPBES Groups

Figure 2. Network relationships between research topics found in the Stage III literature review. Size of nodes relates to the number of publications in that research topic (see Table 1). Blue lines represent positive correlations between topic occurrences. Topics joined by a blue link are more likely to occur in the same document, and orange links represent negative or inverse correlations.

Table 1. The Stage III literature review identified 40,133 abstracts in Scopus about nature’s diverse values. An artificial intelligence (AI) algorithm produced 60 categories that were manually classified by the predominant research topics for each, resulting in 46 categories (30 biophysical, 3 economic, 6 socio-cultural, 1 ILK, and 6 ‘other’). Below is the topic number, research theme, number of articles and top words from the article’s abstract used by the AI to create the cluster.

Topic #	Research domain	Articles n (%)	Top words chosen by the AI to create clusters
1	Biophysical	746 (2%)	plant veget soil grassland speci graze type communiti composit cover
2	Biophysical	550 (1%)	area protect reserv network natur nation zone plan within high
3	Biophysical	791 (2%)	indic index qualiti assess condit environment ecolog valu status use
5	Biophysical	404 (1%)	coastal coast beach zone vulner dune lagoon sand island sea
8	Biophysical	560 (1%)	pollin insect field crop bee bat abund beetl pest flower
10	Biophysical	513 (1%)	mangrov estuari sea bay marsh salin tidal estuarin level rise
19	Biophysical	722 (2%)	conserv biodivers biolog valu prioriti threaten threat loss target ecolog
20	Biophysical	448 (1%)	agricultur product food farm loss farmer degrad system crop farmland
22	Biophysical	570 (1%)	lake water nutrient spring eutroph concentr season phosphorus nitrogen phytoplankton
23	Biophysical	646 (2%)	reef coral seagrass habitat marin bed ecosystem mussel oyster structur
24	Biophysical	264 (1%)	regul carbon suppli water demand servic provis product trade-off storag
25	Biophysical	1049 (3%)	sediment watersh stream catchment soil eros runoff hydrolog flow channel
26	Biophysical	654 (2%)	function trait effect plant communiti respons speci leaf biomass ecosystem
27	Biophysical	747 (2%)	communiti speci abund assemblag differ sampl studi domin divers structur

28	Biophysical	786 (2%)	landscap spatial scale pattern differ connect patch structur heterogen valu
30	Biophysical	377 (1%)	restor ecolog success seed recoveri remov degrad project year establish
32	Biophysical	642 (2%)	speci communiti gradient environment composit structur differ tree plot variabl
37	Biophysical	475 (1%)	model predict use variabl scenario simul suitabl distribut develop optim
40	Biophysical	466 (1%)	genet popul divers gene among sequenc use marker structur high
41	Biophysical	482 (1%)	bird forag breed nest season use winter abund deer select
42	Biophysical	579 (1%)	habitat speci island fragment small endem high abund type studi
43	Biophysical	713 (2%)	land use cover area land-us studi remot chang sens imag
44	Biophysical	371 (1%)	wetland pond water natur import delta peatland rice manag provid
46	Biophysical	775 (2%)	fish marin fisheri ocean sea manag stock catch speci ecosystem
49	Biophysical	750 (2%)	food trophic prey predat speci valu web diet isotop fish
50	Biophysical	437 (1%)	nativ speci invas australia control fire impact alien spread new
55	Biophysical	466 (1%)	distribut across rang dispers pattern wiley john distanc son movement
57	Biophysical	444 (1%)	popul rate growth densiti effect surviv size increas dynam may
58	Biophysical	744 (2%)	speci divers rich group biodivers differ number taxonom sampl use
13	Biophysical	613 (2%)	river flow basin water flood hydrolog riparian floodplain dam freshwat
4	Economic	600 (1%)	access hous qualiti resid properti life home residenti mobil transport

12	Economic	1381 (3%)	ecolog china valu region area result index show studi increas
56	Economic	1537 (4%)	valu cost econom benefit estim valuat per use million result
16	ILK	2203 (5%)	communiti knowledg local stakehold particip involv process group engag valu
9	Other	994 (2%)	chang climat increas impact futur will time global adapt trend
39	Other	2137 (5%)	develop sustain environment resourc econom social integr human environ natur
48	Other	511 (1%)	anim wildlif wild hunt human livestock conflict bear use game
54	Other	1375 (3%)	countri household econom livelihood incom south africa poverti india natur
59	Other	366 (1%)	forest tree manag tropic plantat forestri wood local stand deforest
60	Other	2 (0%)	natur studi inc other close import mani also right
14	Socio-cultural	2078 (5%)	manag risk assess decis approach plan can framework strategi resili
17	Socio-cultural	3998 (10%)	cultur valu ident articl indigen polit natur discours social
21	Socio-cultural	616 (2%)	tourism tourist recreat visitor taylor franci attract group travel studi
38	Socio-cultural	1694 (4%)	ecosystem servic valu provid human assess function benefit provis valuat
47	Socio-cultural	1554 (4%)	cultur landscap heritag rural local tradit region territori valu preserv
52	Socio-cultural	1303 (3%)	park natur peopl place environ design percept prefer garden valu

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